

Nanoscience Dynamics: New Trends by G20

Asst. Prof. Digvijay Gore

Shri. Kumarswami Senior College, Ausa, Latur

Email: digvijaygore7@gmail.com

Mob. No: 9689851056

Abstract

The idea of G20 nations is becoming more and more of a phenomenon. This study attempts to gauge the research productivity of G20 countries in nanoscience. They have been advancing in many scientific disciplines and nanotechnology is no different. Cooperate engagement with nano is triggering the collaborations among the nations for next generation device formation. Nanoscience and nanotechnology investments offer excellent returns and promise to revolutionize science based development strategies benefiting socio-economic vision around the globe. Geopolitics of G20 countries have effects on nanotechnology which will shape the future of the world. This paper will cover the recent advancement in nanoscience in various applications. Thin film is the most targeted topic from a nanofabrication perspective. Here we try to trace some novel trends in nano [1,2].

Keywords: Nanoscience, Socio-economic, G20, Thin film, nanofabrication.

Introduction

Nanoscience is an interdisciplinary subject. Physicist Richard Feynman first proposed the concept of Nano by building things at smaller dimensions. Nanotechnology has been defined as being concerned with materials and systems whose structures and components exhibit novel and significantly improved physical, chemical and biological properties, phenomena and processes due to their nanoscale size [3]. Nanotechnology has transformed science and plays a key role in several innovative aspects of the new generation of devices. The field of nanoscience has the potential to significantly advance global sustainability initiatives. It is a broad subject of study and development that has expanded quickly globally in recent years.

Science is often related to international relations. As a part of G20 summit hosted by India in the year 2023, the Science20 meeting has a theme of 'Transformative Science for Sustainable Development.' G20 countries has a great contribution to the field of Biomedical, information and technological, environmental, agricultural, industrial, educational, economical and financial. The current advancement in science covers the use of nanomaterials in sensors and detectors, memristor, spintronics, drug delivery, solar cells, 3D printing, tissue engineering,

anticancer, shielding agents and many more. Due to an industrial revolution in G20 countries, innovative ideas in nanoscience will be boosted. Nanomaterials have at least one dimension between 1 and 100 nanometres [4]. At this nanoscale level, the material shows very different properties from that of the larger scale. The world has seen enormous political turmoil in the past several years. Four decades after its invention, nanotechnology is still having a significant impact on a wide range of areas and has the potential to transform many more sectors.

Objectives

- There exists a linear trend in the growth of literature in the field of Nanotechnology.
- Collaborative research dominates by G20 nations in the field of Nanotechnology.

Methodology and Database

In order to debate crucial global issues, systemically important industrialised and developing nations came together to form the Group of Twenty (G20) Finance Ministers and Central Bank Governors in 1999.

According to a 2022 report from Clarivate's Institute for Scientific Information, G20 countries accounted for 82% of global research papers in the Web of Science index in 2021. This role has the potential to advance an international scientific community that aligns with the principles of Open Science. Thus, in order to promote worldwide scientific knowledge sharing and foster more economic and international collaboration, the G20 should back efforts being led by UNESCO and other pertinent international organisations to create an Open Research Global platform. There exists number of databases such as Scopus, Engineering Village, Web of Science, Compendex, Inspec, Medlars, Pubmed. Scientometric is a tool by which the state of science and technology can be observed, through the overall production of scientific literature, at a given level of specialization. There are many quality web sources and abstract, citation databases of peer-reviewed literature with smart tools to track, analyze and visualize scientific communication of nanoscience. It is designed to find the Quick, easy and comprehensive information needed. They provide superior support for the literature research process. The Research Priority Index (RPI) of several nations indicates that the research priorities in the various nanotechnology subfields are uniform.

Table: Number of patents filed by each G20 member

Argentina	1239	France	64287	Japan	423264	South Korea	260614
Australia	11907	Germany	168092	Mexico	2102	Turkey	10110
Brazil	7271	India	37895	Russia	30283	UK	53079
Canada	23855	Indonesia	1358	Saudi Arabia	9782	USA	496123
China	1441086	Italy	32551	South Africa	1457		

Source: World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Statistics Data Centre [5]

Figure: Research Collaboration in Nanoscience by G20 Nations

Analysis

G20 nations collaborative work results in the development of nano functional device fabrication. By the year 2023, nanoscience has become an attractive field for research and development investment.

Argentina mentioned use of nanotechnology in agriculture has grown recently and is a useful tool in the global effort to produce food in a sustainable manner. Numerous nanomaterials have

been employed to create delivery systems for bioactive substances with the goal of increasing crop protection and productivity. The complex ecosystem is formed between nano molecules and plants [6].

Thermal energy storage properties enhanced by phase changing nanomaterials is done by **Australia** [7].

Brazil is blessed with the Amazon rainforest. Brazilian researchers report green synthesised silver nanoparticles from Amazonian fruit extract. G20 nations also focused on climate change and sustainable development [8].

Canadian scientists are working on biomimetic sensor using gold nano/micro-islands and molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) for electrochemical detection of heart fatty acid binding protein in human serum [9].

Researchers in **Chinese** formulated a novel nano Silica-wood composite that significantly improved the compact microstructure, thermal and mechanical properties, and hydrophobicity. The results showed that silica sol can penetrate and distribute into the wood cell cavities and the surface of cell walls and hence combine with the substances of wood materials [10].

France quoted that the nanoscience has the potential to provide food security. Food waste can be reduced because of nanotechnology's ability to enhance functional qualities, extend the shelf life, and transport food ingredients to the optimum location. Furthermore, it is feasible to create goods that are healthier and contain fewer infections [11].

Utilising nano spray drying technique for dental implants is come to focus in recent years. It is an innovative biocompatible nanocoating with antibacterial properties. **Germans** suggests to use titanium disc which were used as a model material for dental implants [12].

India concentrated its nano field for the synthesis of various types of gas sensors. Metal oxide gas sensor is the top interest of Indian scholars. The availability of characterization techniques will provide a better platform for the nano research. There is a need for low cost gas sensing devices in upcoming industrial expansion [13,14].

nano-size MgO was synthesized from local seawater bittern obtained from salt industry in **Indonesia** by adopting electrochemical process [15].

Cancer is an dangerous issue spreading around the globe and it is red-flagged by WHO. **Italy** has developed a cancer therapy nanodevice using advances in Hyaluronic Acid Based nano. Herein, surface functionalization of different nanoparticles is studied [16].

most recent developments in laser manufacturing techniques for micro nanoscale products and a thorough examination of uses, including nanojoining and 3D printing is done by **Japan** [17].

Mexico has studied nanoparticles (NPs) that are documented in the brains of children and young adults exposed to Metropolitan Mexico City pollution. Toxicity is a major concern in the modern world. There is a need for NP emission sources to be clearly recognized, regulated, and monitored [18].

Russia manufactured the nano engineering water repellent effect on the fabric manufacturing trendy cloths. Nanotechnology offers promising applications in modern textiles, enhancing aesthetics, breathability, flexibility, and durability without compromising intrinsic properties.

South Africa and Saudi Arabia used Nano antimicrobials as therapeutics. They highlighted multidrug resistivity of microorganisms in the biomedical field [20-22].

South Korea drag the attention of expert stakeholder groups, the media, and the general public on the hazards and advantages of using nanoparticles in food and beverage packaging. Advances and challenges on applications of nanotechnology in food packaging have briefly explored. Nanoscience offers potential for new products and processes in the food and related industries by influencing microstructure, rheology, and functional properties [23].

Nanotechnology in defence is focused by **Turkey** and **UK**. They understand the need to reduce the carrier weight of a soldier by designing lightweight body armour and weapons is focused by scientists. Nanotechnology can enhance defence and security by updating equipment, weapons, and introducing new functions and devices [24].

USA also developed DNA nanotechnology for the field of medical science. They use nanobots for drug delivery. Nanotechnology in the field of energy storage is an emerging field currently. The electrodes of a supercapacitor can be formed by triggering electric properties of the material at the nanoscale. [25]

Conclusion

Our G20 Research Report draw on our unique science insights to offer analysis, ideas and commentary to enlighten and stimulate debate. We observe a linear growth in the field of Nanotechnology for G20 Nations. Those nations developed collaborative nanoscience research dominates. Nanotechnologies can enhance the competitiveness of renewable biomaterials by reducing supply chain costs and adding functionality, enhancing their use in smart packaging, E-paper, advanced engineering, and cosmetics. over the past two decades, China accounted for the highest number of citations and the most publications followed by India and Iran. while Saudi Arabia and Vietnam show the highest international collaboration level. G20 nations has also played a central role in the collaboration network among the rest of the world.

Reference

- [1] Kagan, C., Fernandez, L., Gogotsi, Y., Hammond, P., Hersam, M., Nel, A., Penner, R., Willson, C., & Weiss, P. (2016). Nano Day: Celebrating the Next Decade of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology. *ACS nano*, 9093-9103. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.6b06655>
- [2] Sozer, N., & Kokini, J. (2009). Nanotechnology and its applications in the food sector. *Trends in biotechnology*, 27 2, 82-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2008.10.010>
- [3] E. Inshakova and A. Inshakova, "Nanomaterials and nanotechnology: Prospects for technological re-equipment in the power engineering industry," *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 709, no. 3, 2020, <http://doi:10.1088/1757-899X/709/3/033020>
- [4] A. Dey, "Semiconductor metal oxide gas sensors: A review," *Mater. Sci. Eng. B Solid State Mater. Adv. Technol.*, vol. 229, no. November 2017, pp. 206–217, 2018, <https://doi:10.1016/j.mseb.2017.12.036>
- [5] World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Statistics Data Centre
- [6] Fiol, D. F., Terrile, M. C., Frik, J., Mesas, F. A., Álvarez, V. A., & Casalongué, C. A. (2021). Nanotechnology in plants: Recent advances and challenges. *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, 96(8), 2095-2108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.6741>
- [7] Mohammadpour, J., Lee, A., Timchenko, V., & Taylor, R. (2022). Nano-enhanced phase change materials for thermal energy storage: a bibliometric analysis. *Energies*, 15(9), 3426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15093426>
- [8] Lima, A. K. O., Vasconcelos, A. A., Sousa Júnior, J. J. V., Escher, S. K. S., Nakazato, G., & Taube Júnior, P. S. (2019). Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using Amazon fruits. *International Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, 15(3), 179-188.
- [9] A. Sanati, R. S. Moakhar, K. Raeissi, F. Karimzadeh, H. Vali and S. Mahshid, "Detection of heart-fatty acid binding protein in human serum using gold nano/micro-islands and molecularly imprinted polymers," *2021 IEEE 21st International Conference on Nanotechnology (NANO)*, Montreal, QC, Canada, 2021, pp. 397-399, doi: 10.1109/NANO51122.2021.95143377
- [10] Xu, E., Zhang, Y., & Lin, L. (2020). Improvement of mechanical, hydrophobicity and thermal properties of Chinese fir wood by impregnation of nano silica sol. *Polymers*, 12(8), 1632. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12081632>
- [11] Sercan, D. E. D. E. Nano-foods to provide a long shelf life to be able to reduce the amount of food-waste.

- [12] Baghdan, E., Raschpichler, M., Lutfi, W., Pinnapireddy, S. R., Pourasghar, M., Schäfer, J., ... & Bakowsky, U. (2019). Nano spray dried antibacterial coatings for dental implants. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, 139, 59-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2019.03.003>
- [13] Dey, "Semiconductor metal oxide gas sensors: A review," *Mater. Sci. Eng. B SolidState Mater. Adv. Technol.*, vol. 229, no. November 2017, pp. 206–217, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.mseb.2017.12.036.
- [14] A. Singh, S. Sikarwar, A. Verma, and B. Chandra Yadav, "The recent development of metal oxide heterostructures based gas sensor, their future opportunities and challenges: A review," *Sensors Actuators A Phys.*, vol. 332, p. 113127, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.SNA.2021.113127
- [15] Hanif Amrulloh, Wasinton Simanjuntak, Rudy Tahan Mangapul , Sophia Lasma Sagala, Rikha Bramawanto, Awalul Fatiqin, Ridho Nahrowi & Mai Zuniati (2020) Preparation of nano-magnesium oxide from Indonesia local seawater bittern using the electrochemical method, *Inorganic and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, 50:8, 693-698, DOI: [10.1080/24701556.2020.1724146](https://doi.org/10.1080/24701556.2020.1724146)
- [16] Della Sala, F., Fabozzi, A., di Gennaro, M., Nuzzo, S., Makvandi, P., Solimando, N., ... & Borzacchiello, A. (2022). Advances in Hyaluronic-Acid-Based (Nano) Devices for Cancer Therapy. *Macromolecular Bioscience*, 22(1), 2100304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.202100304>
- [17] Hu, A. (Ed.). (2020). *Laser Micro-nano-manufacturing and 3D Microprinting*. Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer.
- [18] Calderón-Garcidueñas, L., González-Maciel, A., Reynoso-Robles, R., Silva-Pereyra, H. G., Torres-Jardón, R., Brito-Aguilar, R., ... & Delgado-Chávez, R. (2022). Environmentally toxic solid nanoparticles in noradrenergic and dopaminergic nuclei and cerebellum of metropolitan Mexico City children and young adults with neural quadruple misfolded protein pathologies and high exposures to nano particulate matter. *Toxics*, 10(4), 164. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10040164>
- [20] Wang, X. X., Cao, W. Q., Cao, M. S., & Yuan, J. (2020). Assembling nano–microarchitecture for electromagnetic absorbers and smart devices. *Advanced materials*, 32(36), 2002112.
- [21] Miyazaki, K., & Islam, N. (2007). Nanotechnology systems of innovation - An analysis of industry and academia research activities. *Technovation*, 27, 661-675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TECHNOVATION.2007.05.009>
- [22] Sanguansri, P., & Augustin, M. (2006). Nanoscale materials development - a food industry perspective. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 17, 547-556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2006.04.010>
- [23] Enescu, D., Cerqueira, M. A., Fucinos, P., & Pastrana, L. M. (2019). Recent advances and challenges on applications of nanotechnology in food packaging. A literature review. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 134, 110814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2019.110814>
- [24] Jafari, M., & Zarghami, H. (2016). Measuring nanotechnology development through the study of the dividing pattern between developed and developing countries during 2000–2014. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 18, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-016-3431-0>
- [25] DeLuca, M., Shi, Z., Castro, C. E., & Arya, G. (2020). Dynamic DNA nanotechnology: toward functional nanoscale devices. *Nanoscale Horizons*, 5(2), 182-201. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9NH00529C>